

OWID: Optimizing Wound Healing Individually

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Abstract: Chronic wounds represent a dysfunction of the intrinsic wound healing process. Advanced wound healing therapies apply exogenous biophysical stimulation such as photobiomodulation, mechanical or electrical stimulation to influence wound healing. This project provides a control systems perspective and engineering modeling approach for technical support of wound treatment therapy. Exogenous treatment controller modulation of the wound healing system is, for the first time, presented as a closed-loop feedback control system to guide wound healing treatment therapy research. The system components are introduced relative to the research to date. The overall closed-loop feedback control system is described for the light system, wound system, and treatment control system. Coupled feedback loop block diagrams of the treatment (stimulation loop) and physiology (wound loop) feedback loops are combined to create a full system, closed-loop feedback control model for wound healing. A stimulation loop includes treatment inputs and growth output. A simple approach of using the simulation control loop and a valid model for cell dynamics to design a controller is suggested. A feedback loop is shown whereby light is an additional controlled input, compared to the physiological healing process. This presentation of the integration of these works into block diagrams for modulation and control of the wound healing system supports the overall research goal of automated patient specific wound healing.

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I. Introduction

Wound healing is a physiological process of repair of a tissue that has been structurally damaged. Advanced wound healing therapies apply exogenous biophysical stimulation to influence wound healing processes. In particular, photobiomodulation applies light treatment and has shown biological effects using red, green and blue wavelengths [1]. A biphasic dose-response is observed in photobiomodulation, where lower light doses activate biological activity up to a threshold dosage, then increasing doses have an inhibitory effect [2]. Although treatment parameters determine the outcome of biological responses, optimal treatment parameters remain undefined and there are no standard protocols used to guide wound healing treatment therapy.

In the OWID project a systematic evaluation of photobiomodulation on 3D dermal tissue equivalents was conducted. Different wavelength and dose responses on human tissue drafts over time were accessed via cell response markers and visual wound closure.

II. Material and methods

A device was constructed to apply three wavelengths (Fig. 1) and doses in an incubator on living 3D human dermal

Figure 1: Left: Spectral irradiance for different intensity settings of the LED drivers (18%, 56% and 100%), measured for each color with LED at a distance of 53 mm. Accuracy of measurements at 4%.

tissue cell cultures. In addition, mechanical and electrical stimulation was prepared but not systematically evaluated.

II.I. Biological Data and Experiment design

Early in the project different skin models (with and without integration of melanocytes) were cultivated according to [6, 10], a standardized incision method to generate reproducible wound defects was developed [5] and the evaluation of wound healing parameters standardized using immunofluorescence and histological staining:

- Keratin 17 for the open wound
- Keratin 1/10 for the normalized epidermis
- Laminin, fibrinogen collagen IV for the normalized basement membrane
- alpha smooth muscle actin for the activated fibroblasts
- Detection of matrix metalloproteases and collagen staining Elastica according to van Gieson for remodeling and structure of the collagen matrix

For each radiation experiment (red, blue, green light at 100% or 50%) at least 12 cell cultures were treated equally over 3 weeks to compensate for uncontrolled influence factors. At each time point one culture was sacrificed and evaluated.

As two controls the extend of unaffected cell healing and with added growth factors (e.g. KGF) – but both without any technical influence – were determined after 1, 2 and 3 weeks [11].

II.II. Reproducible wounding and wound area determination

Given 3D dermal equivalents in cell cultures, a simple reproducible and sufficiently accurate wounding was established to reach comparable start conditions during the experiments. Automatic image planimetry [5,7,11] was

applied to compare different wounding techniques, with 3 subjects repeating wound healing multiple times to include training effects [5].

II.III. Modelling

Several approaches were implemented and evaluated to model the influence of technical means on the wound healing process [6,8,12] and especially the cell migration and cell growth under stimulating and inhibiting factors. With sensitivity analysis the major factors of wound healing control were identified.

III. Results and discussion

This project introduced wound healing process manipulation with technical means [13]. A device for photobiomodulation was developed and integrated into an incubator [4], that was able to. Special attention was required to avoid diffusing chemicals that may damage the cell cultures. The optical properties of the photobiomodulation device were analysed to understand the dosage that reached the cells (Fig 1).

Figure 2: Photobiomodulation device above cell culture plates. Duration and intensity of radiation is controlled via a PC.

A 3D human skin model was established [10], wounded with a reproducible, accurate wounding process and its size and change determined by an image based planimetry system [5, 7, 11]. To create a model-based individualized wound healing control system [9, 14] different mathematical models of wound healing were implemented and compared [6, 8] and parameter sensitivity investigated [12].

Figure 3: Matrixmetalloproteinasen MMP-2 at different time points (after 7 days -T7, after 11 days- T11 and after 17 days T17) during wound healing. Cell cultures were untreated (grey), or treated with red light with full intensity (dark red) or 50% (light red) or received blue light with full (dark blue) or 50% radiation (light blue).

In three experimental trials with different wavelength and strength of photobiomodulation the effect on cell activation and growth was obtained and evaluated. One of the results shows, that wound healing is sensitive to the timing of the different wavelengths evaluated (Fig. 2).

IV. Conclusions

This project investigated wound healing properties of human dermal cells. In standardized experiments first results were obtained confirming the overall complexity of technical wound healing support. Mathematical modelling showed a certain promise to better understand the process of exogenous biophysical stimulation, which might finally lead to a closed loop individualized wound healing therapy.

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